

Notes on key performance indicators

Supplement to

- “Base4NFDI service Integration Procedures”:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15235863>
- “Requirements for Completion of the Integration Phase”:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17107044>
- “Requirements for Completion of the Ramp-up Phase”:
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Overview

The service team’s efforts will more or less end with the completion of the ramp up phase, but the service itself will enter another, its operational phase, and it will be part of the Base4NFDI service portfolio. For reporting its success over time and in order not to miss the point at which the service is no longer used, there will have to be appropriate monitoring. To this end, the service teams will have to provide key performance indicators which are relevant to the service, objective, and measurable. Typical indicators could come from these categories:

1. **Users:** number of users or of working groups, total / per day, ...
2. **Scope:** number of involved consortia, number of workshops, publications, subscribers, page visits, ...
3. **Usage:** CPU time, storage, data volume transferred, ...
4. **Items:** number of commits, posts, tickets, files, folders, ...
5. **Instances:** number of virtual machines, Jupyter applications, projects, ...

For a more extensive list to choose or get inspiration from, see below.

The teams need to provide only the raw metrics (like number of users per month) without any normalisation, aggregation, or statistics. Base4NFDI will take care of all of this.

The system for collecting the raw data, its interfaces, and the formatting standards are still to be developed, but the teams should be prepared to implement a scheme for automatic generation and upload of their metrics at regular intervals, at latest during the Ramp-Up Phase. Most probably, the data will have to be provided in some standardized CSV format and uploaded to a Gitlab repository. The details of this will be figured out in the course of 2025.

Details and recommendations

The following section lists KPI metrics that may be applied to a service. It is intended as a starting point for consideration: Some services might need other metrics which are not yet on the list and not every metric given here will make sense for every service. We recommend choosing a meaningful set of user-related and usage-related KPIs, and - if possible - to distinguish between relevant target groups like NFDI, consortia, and EOSC.

Possible KPIs related to ...

... users: persons/groups

- number of users
- number of groups or virtual organisations

... users: scope/outreach

- number of involved consortia
- number of involved research associations
- number of using organisations
- number of trainings/workshops
- number of training/workshop hours
- number of training documents
- number of publications or presentations
- number of citations
- number of requests
- number of subscribe
- number of applications or proposals
- number of actions
- number of page views or visits
- number of service incubators
- duration of visits

... usage: resources

- CPU hours used
- memory used

- storage used
- data volume transferred
- repository size
- wiki size

... usage: service-specific items

- number of folders, files, or documents
- number of tickets processed
- number of defects fixed
- number of commits
- number of posts
- number of surveys
- number of up-/downloads
- number of catalogue items
- number of connected services
- number of connected sites
- number of minted PIDs
- number of provided TS widgets

... usage: service-specific instances

- number of VMs
- number of Pods
- number of Jupyter applications
- number of projects
- number of executions
- number of rolled out technical applications

... other

- number of legacy services retired in favour of the new central one

Possible modifiers and qualifiers

A single raw figure might not be meaningful on its own and would benefit from some context. Here are some examples of possible specifications that might help to better qualify the metrics and to distinguish between different contexts.

- registered vs. anonymous users or groups
- registered vs. active users or groups

- total number of visits/items vs. number/items per day, week, or month
- total number of visits vs. number of unique visits

- total number of items vs. number of items per visit

- total number or amount of users, services, trainings, storage, ...
- vs.

- number or amount related to NFDI, EOSC, specific consortia, or other entities

If possible, service teams should consider employing context-relevant qualifiers (last example above) as this would help Base4NFDI to document its outreach within the different communities.